

FAIRragro

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FAIRragro Workshop: Geodata quality in the application of agricultural system data

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Acronyms

DFFP Data-Fitness-For-Purpose. [0](#), [2](#), [4-6](#), [8-10](#), [E](#)

DDFU Data-Fitness-For-Use. [0](#), [2](#), [4-6](#), [8](#), [H](#)

DMP Data Management Plan. [10](#), [H](#)

FDO [FAIR Digital Object](#). [7](#), [10](#), [H](#)

PID Persistent Identifier. [10](#)

RDF [Resource Description Framework](#). [5](#)

1. Introduction

Comprehensive information on data quality enables data users to independently assess the suitability of a data set for their specific purpose. The current [FAIRagro survey on data quality](#) shows that data quality tests are already being carried out in the agricultural science community but are rarely documented due to lack of time, knowledge, or infrastructure.

To address the topic, the workshop **“Geodata Quality in the Application of Agrosystem Data”** was organized by [FAIRagro-Measure 3.3](#), which took place on 6 and 7 June 2024 in Braunschweig with 20 participants from the agricultural science community. These included FAIRagro employees from various task areas, people from different institutions of the co-applicants and participants (JKI, Thünen, UFZ) as well as from industry.

In addition to identifying the user-specific requirements for data quality information ([Group work on data quality](#)), the status of the existing digital infrastructure was discussed ([Keynote: Metadata Concepts in FAIRagro \(Daniel Martini, KTBL\)](#)) and [Impulse talk: Introduction of JKI and Geodata Management \(GDM\) group \(Markus Möller, JKI\)](#) and the user-specific requirements for quality information for [DDFU/DDFP](#) assessment were worked out ([Keynote: Fitness-For-Use/Purpose \(Julia Fischer, UFZ\)](#) and [Group work on data-fitness-for-purpose](#)).

Figure 1: Group picture of workshop participants

2. Workshop elements

2.1. Impulse talk: Introduction of JKI and Geodata Management (GDM) group (Markus Möller, JKI)

As the first contribution to the workshop, Markus Möller presented the Julius Kuehn-Institute (JKI) as the workshop organizer and its digital geodata infrastructure. This is dominated by the paradigm shift from local data processing to cloud computing, which includes data cubes and web services. One of the current challenges in geodata management is the assurance of data quality. Although many standards already exist, the problem often lies in their implementation. This raises the question of how routines for the description of the geodata quality in scientific practice can be established.

2.2. Impulse talk: Introduction of FAIRagro (Carsten Hoffmann, ZALF)

[FAIRagro](#) is a consortium of the National Research Data Infrastructure ([NFDI](#)), which aims to manage the organisation of the various research institutions in a better coordinated, standardised and connected network. The overarching goals of the NFDI are “making data FAIR” and the vision of “finding the right dataset, understanding its content easily/quickly and reusing it for a new purpose”.

FAIRagro consists of eleven (co-)applicants and 18 participants and covers the agricultural sciences community with the topics plants, soil and environment (Ewert et al., [2023](#)). The biggest challenge in research data management is dealing with different scales, disciplines, and data categories. The motivation of FAIRagro-Task Area 3 is that the research data infrastructure must not only be FAIR, but also support researchers in questions of data quality and offer legal certainty.

2.3. Impulse talk: Introduction to Data Quality (Jannes Uhlott, JKI)

Good quality data generates trust and is reliable and usable. Data quality ensures that the data complies with legal requirements and saves enormous costs, as it is much more expensive to correct products afterwards instead of making them qualitative directly. Increasing data quality helps scientists to trust the platform of their choice more (e.g., due to clear rules and criteria), and they are more willing to share their own data. Information about the usability of a product enables users to make their own judgment about the (re)usability of the product for their purpose. The additional information also ensures that the quality can be assessed and is not under- or overestimated (Lacagnina et al., [2023](#)).

Data quality is defined by ISO 19157-1, 2023 as “degree to which a set of inherent characteristics of data fulfills a requirement”. Data quality can be described by data quality dimensions, which are for example (Fischer et al., 2023; Quarati et al., 2021):

Accuracy extent to which data correctly describes the real-world object or event,

Completeness degree to which all required data is present,

Consistency absence of differences when comparing two or more instances of data,

Timeliness extent to which data is up to date and available when needed,

Validity degree to which data conforms to the rules and constraints defined for it,

Reliability degree of trustworthiness,

Integrity accuracy and consistency of data over its lifecycle.

The relevant quality dimensions differ according to the source and area of application. According to ISO 19157-1, 2023, the following data quality elements **completeness, logical consistency, positional accuracy, temporal quality, thematic quality, meta quality** are specified, which can then be subdivided by further sub-elements. The relevance of individual data quality aspects also depends on the phase of the data life cycle in which they are to be described (Peng, 2018; Ramapriyan et al., 2017). According to ISO 19157-1, 2023, quality information should be stored as short and generally structured information in the metadata to enable interoperability. In addition, more detailed information should be described in a quality evaluation report, which is then linked in the metadata.

2.4. Keynote: Metadata Concepts in FAIRagro (Daniel Martini, KTBL)

One of the two keynote presentations was given by Daniel Martini (KTBL) on metadata concepts in FAIRagro. The DFFU/DFFP approach plays a key role here, whereby a comprehensive description of the data enables it to be used for a specific purpose. However, the definition is very open and flexible, as the properties depend heavily on the utilization and therefore the user-specific requirements (RfII - Rat für Informationsinfrastrukturen, 2020).

In the new development of data science, data and metadata themselves become the research product. In addition, machine learning requires large amounts of data, whereby the training data should be as heterogeneous as possible, i.e. it should also include low-quality data. When considering the data life cycle, metadata can be continuously added, which generates a lot of metadata and enables a user evaluation of usefulness.

According to the FAIR principles, metadata should use a formal, accessible, shared and widely applicable language for knowledge representation. Currently, linked metadata in

[Resource Description Framework \(RDF\)](#) (Resource Description Framework) is considered the best option, as recommended by [European Open Science Cloud \(EOSC\)](#). [RDF statements](#) consisting of subject, predicate, and object are used for the description. It also enables machine-readable links to defined terms in [vocabularies](#), such as AGROVOC (Subirats-Coll et al., 2022).

The [Data Quality Vocabulary \(DQV\)](#), combined with [schema.org](#), already offers fields for describing and evaluating data quality such as *dqv:QualityMeasurement*, *dqv:Metric*, *dqv:Dimension*, *dqv:QualityAnnotation*, *dqv:QualityCertificate*, *dqv:UserQualityFeedback*.

In this context, [DFFU/DFFP](#) can be considered an open concept, in which data quality is viewed as an evolving metadata continuum. Metadata representations must therefore support arbitrary additions over time, arbitrary metadata depth and distributed annotations. The FAIR principles provide guidance for this, which is currently supported by [RDF](#)-based metadata standards, including specific [RDF](#) vocabularies to describe data quality (Mons et al., 2017).

2.5. Postersession

- **Analyzing and improving data quality by an interactive interface for quality metrics** by Sven Gedicke, Shiyaza Risvi, Jan-Hendrik Hauernt
- **Facilitate Soil and Agricultural Geodata Quality: Join the DQ-Kit Open-Source Initiative at the BonaRes Repository** by Susanne Lachmuth, Carsten Hoffmann, Viet Hoang Nguyen, Igo Silva de Almeida, Torsten Thalheim, Bethia Kynn, Stephan Lesch, Sebastian Rick, Thomas Kühnert, Xenia Specka, Nikolai Svoboda
- **IACS data: quality assessment and improvements exemplifying architecture, quality checks and results** by Heinz Behle, Boineelo Moyo
- **Streamlining Pest and Disease data UC3 Action 2: Towards improved FAIRness** by Stefan Kühnel, Christina Wagner, Marissa Lorenzen, Jörg Sellmann, Til Feike

2.6. Impulse talk: Results of FAIRagro survey – Data quality in the application of agricultural system data (Jannes Uhlott, JKI)

The survey “data quality in the application of agricultural system data” was available from November 14, 2023, to January 21, 2024 in the online tool LimeSurvey. The link to the questionnaire was distributed through the FAIRagro website, newsletter, mailing list, and social media channels, as well as with the assistance of the FAIRagro plenary among the institutions of the FAIRagro (co)applicants and participants. 321 individuals participated in the

survey, with 211 of them completing it. The questionnaire comprised 27 questions in 5 groups covering topics such as data collection, data use, and data reuse in practice using various question types (single and multiple choice, free text, ranking, etc.).

The survey results provide insight into the needs of our consortium and community regarding the data sets used, user needs, and data quality in agrosystem research and offer further guidance for future work on data quality in combination with DFFU/DFFP. In general, it recognizes that methods for documenting data quality are already being implemented so that relevant data quality criteria could be identified. The results demonstrate that the relevance of different data quality criteria varies across data types, categories and application areas. The biggest challenge for data quality was identified as the lack of time, supplemented by the lack of standards in data collection, data quality, and metadata. In general, the term and concept behind metadata remains still relatively unknown within the community, indicating a need for additional information on data quality and metadata through training and other resources (such as fact sheets, blogs, and OER). In addition, the survey results prove that a large part of researchers are willing to spend up to two hours per data set in quality assurance documentation. Both the survey itself and the derived data are published (Uhlott et al., 2024).

2.7. Group work on data quality

The results of the data quality survey (section 2.6) were further discussed in four small groups. The groups were divided according to the topics 1. Personal and social benefits of data quality, 2. time saving in data quality management, 3. seal of data quality and “data quality codex” and 4. explanatory materials for data quality. The original answers can be found as photos in the appendix A.

Personal and social benefits of data quality

Publishing data and being open about its quality increases the likelihood that these data will be reused and cited, as it appears more trustworthy. It is recommended that knowledge about data quality is imparted during university studies. In order to increase the motivation to publish data, such publications could be made a prerequisite for project funding, which would also increase the publication numbers of researchers and institutes. This could also boost the intrinsic motivation of researchers as their publicly accessible data could be reused. An open approach to data quality information could become established if a critical mass of users adopt this approach, and it is seen as a matter of course. An open error culture could help to lower the inhibition threshold for publication.

Time saving in data quality management

Automating as many steps as possible when describing data and its quality is the main method for saving time and reducing errors in the future. However, this would require the data categories and types to be consistent, which is made difficult by the heterogeneous data basis in the agricultural community. Initial approaches could therefore consist of data type-independent methods such as the automatic derivation of the geographical extent. In addition, existing processes should be better documented and made more accessible, for example through mentoring programs and wikis that impart knowledge about tools and workflows. In addition, more structured queries and templates should be used to minimize free text fields and use integrated, expandable vocabularies instead. A supplementary feedback system could forward comments to the authors and make them accessible to other users.

'Seal' of data quality

A potential seal of quality should not be awarded by a person or institution, but by a neutral tool. A rating system could take the form of stars, whereby, for example, one star is awarded for existing metadata and a second star for additional data quality information. However, it is often only possible to check the content of the data using specialized knowledge, which is difficult to automate. If such a check is carried out by individual users, it should be documented in detail and in a comprehensible manner. In addition, there is a general fear that data could be categorized as "bad data". For this reason, there should be free text fields in which negative assessments could be explained.

Data quality 'codex'

The idea of a "data codex" aims to pass on the basics of data quality and data management directly to young researchers, ideally as part of their degree program. Students should be made aware of the personal benefits of FAIR data in order to increase their intrinsic motivation.

Explanatory materials for data quality

An interactive guide in the form of a decision tree and a modular structure is identified as a suitable structure to provide information material on data quality. This could be supplemented by a glossary and templates on data quality. Consideration should also be given to how data quality can be integrated into the design of research data management plans (e.g., as [FAIR Digital Object \(FDO\)](#)).

2.8. Impulse talk: Application of DFFU/DFFP (Markus Möller, JKI)

As an example of the data-fitness-for-purpose approach, the impact of soil maps of different scales on the derivation of soil functions like yield potential was presented. This emphasizes the need for a critical review of the quality of input data and a structure (e.g., knowledge graphs) for formalization of DFFU/DFFP.

2.9. Keynote: Fitness-For-Use/Purpose (Julia Fischer, UFZ)

The second keynote on the topic of Data-Fitness-for-Purpose (DFFP) was presented by Julia Fischer from Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung (UFZ, Leipzig) about the results of the project GeoKur. The difference between DFFU and DFFP was illustrated using the example of a precipitation time series. DFFU maps the non-functional requirements, which are independent of the application area. Applied to a precipitation dataset, this would be, for example, the condition that no negative values are present. DFFP, on the other hand, maps the functional requirements. In the example of a planned weekly time series, the condition that weekly measured values are available in the data set would have to be fulfilled. The aim of DFFP is therefore to provide sufficient information to enable users to decide on their own whether the data fulfill their specific purpose. The important elements of DFFP are the quality of the data, the provenance and the ontology.

A survey (n=33) emphasized the importance of provenance information and showed that some information is available in metadata, but others are hidden in written reports. Case studies (n=3) compared different quality metrics and recommended making quality information findable and accessible and explicitly documenting it in terms of space and time. In addition, definitions (for example, different definitions of forest) and ontologies as well as provenance information should be linked.

The geodashboard of the GeoKur project enables a fit-for-purpose check, standardized metadata and the graphical representation of various input data. Data quality metrics can thus be used for DFFP assessments or comparisons. In order to provide data users with the best possible support, flexible metadata fields and provenance information should be integrated into the dataset documentation and made available by the data producers.

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2.10. Group work on data-fitness-for-purpose

Various data types were discussed in small groups in order to identify the user-specific requirements for purpose evaluation. The groups were divided into 1. timeseries, 2. drone data and 3. big geodata. The original answers can be found as photos in the appendix [A](#).

Time series

The following information is required for the evaluation of [DFFP](#) for time series: temporal and spatial coverage and resolution, methodology, technical metadata on devices, sensors and instruments, relevant boundary conditions (e.g. weather, time source for GPS), whether values were measured or interpolated and any method changes within the time series. The presentation should be in tabular form with colored highlights.

Drone data

Technical information (formats, resolution, coordinate systems, bands used, sensor properties) and data collection details (pilot, weather, air pressure, wind speed, real-time kinematic positioning (RTK), field management) are required for the purpose of evaluation of drone data. Information about the drone (type, manufacturer, date of purchase) as well as data processing and possible interpolation are also relevant. The presentation should be standardized, tabular, and machine-readable.

Big geodata

Due to the large and constantly growing volume, 'big' geodata cannot be stored in repositories and cannot be provided with [Persistent Identifier \(PID\)](#)s. Instead, documentation-specific interfaces should be created. Information on coverage, spatial and temporal resolution and the degree of aggregation is necessary for the purpose evaluation. Data should also contain local quality measures and interpretation aids. In general, a new identifier is required for dynamically growing data (Klump, [2024](#); Klump et al., [2023](#); Klump et al., [2021](#)).

3. Feedback

In order to obtain feedback on the content of the workshop, interactive feedback was implemented with [Mentimeter](#). The complete results are presented in the appendix [A](#).

3.1. Which of the aspects developed today do you hope to get most out of?

The aspects that most people are hoping for are tools for metadata formats and for enhancement of metadata as well as metadata templates. In addition, more data quality concepts, automation and standardized data quality fields in standardized metadata plus optional free text fields are desired. Furthermore, there should now be more clarity about what the next steps could look like.

3.2. What will you implement yourself in your day-to-day work?

The participants state that they want to test and use existing tools and templates such as the R-packages [provo](#) and [pror](#). They are also more aware of the importance of data quality, so they want to increasingly integrate this into their own documentation and metadata. There is also the idea of thinking [Data Management Plan \(DMP\)](#) together with [FDOs](#) in the future and the motivation to identify further community requirements for data quality in the future.

4. Conclusion

The workshop "Data Quality in the Application of Agrosystem Data" held on June 6-7, 2024 in Braunschweig focused extensively on data quality and the [DFFP](#) approach. It was highlighted that fostering an open error culture and developing supportive tools can significantly increase researchers' intrinsic motivation to regularly publish data and data quality information. This should be taught to young researchers during their studies in order to achieve

a critical mass that regularly publishes data and its documentation, which would increase the numbers of publications for both individual researchers and institutes.

To develop suitable tools that support, motivate and save time for researchers, relevant aspects of data quality were identified. This includes general data set properties such as temporal and spatial resolution and coverage as well as methodological details (e.g., changing methodology during an experiment), specific information about measurement techniques (sensors and instruments), and external influences (e.g., meteorological conditions like rain or solar radiation). The presentation of these data should be standardized, tabular and machine-readable, ideally with initial evaluations indicated by color-coding.

A comprehensive dataset description supports the data-fitness-for-purpose approach, enabling users to assess the suitability of the data for their specific purposes based on the provided information on their own.

The workshop results offer FAIRagro, as an NFDI consortium, the opportunity to incorporate user-specific requirements for agrosystem data into the development of future tools.

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We would like to thank all participants for their willingness to participate in the workshop, as well as all presenters who enriched the workshop with their knowledge and ideas.

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A. Appendix

Original answers of group work about data quality

The results of the data quality survey (section 2.6) were further discussed in four small groups. The groups were divided according to the topics 1. Personal and social benefits of data quality, 2. time saving in data quality management, 3. seal of data quality and “data quality codex” and 4. explanatory materials for data quality.

Figure 2: Results of group work about benefits of data quality.

Figure 3: Results of group work about time saving regarding data quality and documentation.

Figure 4: Results of group work about a seal of data quality and a 'data quality codex'.

Figure 5: Results of group work about explanatory materials for data quality.

Original answers of group work on DFFP

Various data types were discussed in small groups in order to identify the user-specific requirements for purpose evaluation. The groups were divided into 1. timeseries, 2. drone data and 3. big geodata.

Figure 6: Results of group work about data-fitness-for-purpose requirements on times series.

Figure 7: Results of group work about data-fitness-for-purpose requirements on drone data.

Figure 8: Results of group work about data-fitness-for-purpose requirements on big geo-data.

Feedback

In order to obtain feedback on the content of the workshop, interactive feedback was implemented with [Mentimeter](#). Each participant could answer the questions and vote on the answers of the others. The number of votes is shown in brackets after the answer.

Which of the aspects developed today do you hope to get most out of?

- Usage of re3data.org, Eppocodes and RDF as a useable metadataformat (5)
- Tools for metadata enhancement (5)
- Metadata templates (5)
- I have more clarity about what the next steps could be (5)
- Concepts for integrating data quality into metadata
- Relevant data quality information
- Existing data quality tool, concepts, projects (5)
- standardisierte Datenqualitätsfelder in standardisierten Metadaten plus optionale Freitextfelder (4)
- domain and data specific automation (3)
- What tools are available? What are the best practices to use them? (2)
- How to promote benefits of providing data quality information (1)
- Concrete information demands to determine DFFU (0)

What will you implement yourself in your day-to-day work?

- Check out existing tools and templates (7)
- Looking into R-packages provo and provr (6)
- Be more conscious about importance of data quality (5)
- Metadata aggregation (5)
- DMP und FDOs zusammen denken und weiter entwickeln (4)
- Data quality metrics metadata examples (4)
- Versuche, mehr data quality in der Dokumentation meiner Daten zu integrieren und warten auf mehr automatisierte Tools (4)
- Try out recommended packages and tools (3)
- Check data quality more consciously (1)
- Weitere community Anforderungen an Datenqualität identifizieren (1)

What I still wanted to say:

- Well done :)
- Tankyou
- Danke für die tolle Organisation des Workshops!
- Thanks Jannes for all the ora stuff
- Danke!
- ([...]) Veranstaltung mega cool
- Wir sollten über die Verstetigung des Themas nachdenken
- Datenqualität in den Agrarwissenschaften ist ein recht weißes Blatt, dass wir füllen sollten (große Chance)

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